

Quantum Space-time Relation for both Massive Particles and Photons from Relativity Part 3

Francesco R. Ruggeri Ha4well, N.B. May 26, 2025

Newtonian mechanics seems to have been developed specifically for a particle with rest mass, m_0 , given that $KE = \frac{1}{2}m_0v^2$ and $p = m_0v$. In other words, it was not developed for the notion of a photon which has the same speed in all frames. Newton apparently believed that a photon was a particle, but by the early 1800s, due to Young's interference experiments, it was believed that the photon was a wave.

We argue here that special relativity introduces two fundamental concepts not present in Newtonian mechanics:

- (A) Special relativity must include both a particle with rest mass and a particle without rest mass which has the same speed in all frames (the photon) in equations written in terms of E, p .
- (B) Special relativity intertwines space-time with E, p , which together with ((A) leads to the notion of E and p being linked to gradations (periodicity) in space and time, we argue. This, in turn, may be the root of free particle quantum mechanics.

We suggest that special relativity forces one to derive relations for x, t, E, p which apply to both a photon and particle with rest mass and that it is these equations which lead to: $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ ((1)). The \hbar factor comes from photon considerations, but also applies to a particle with rest mass because the overall equations apply to both. We consider two sets of intertwined equations: $-Et + px = -E't' + p'x'$ and $E^2 - pc^2 = 0$. Both lead to ((1)).

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics seems to have been designed for a particle with rest mass, given that $p = \text{momentum} = m_0v$ and $KE = \frac{1}{2}m_0v^2$. These definitions do not apply to a particle with zero rest mass. Furthermore, the notion of acceleration means that v can always be increased. Newton apparently thought that a photon was a particle. Later in the early 1800s, Young's interference experiments suggested that a photon was a wave. In other words, it seems that Newtonian mechanics would then be applied to a medium (like in the case of a wave on a string or water wave) and not to the wave disturbance itself. In such a case:

$$v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength} \quad ((2))$$

is the equation assigned to a wave. It seems that originally it may not even have been known if a photon's momentum (given by integral $d\text{space } 1/\mu_0 \text{ Electric field} \times \text{Magnetic field}$) behaved like that of a particle with rest mass in terms of impulse hits. Now it is known that this is the case.

Special Relativity

We ask: What is special relativity? Given Galilean invariance, it might seem to be a theory regarding relative speeds only. If one considers the case of a particle with rest mass, m_0 , as in Newtonian mechanics and analyzes how this particle is viewed in a frame moving with constant speed $-v$, then:

Rest Mass Viewpoint

- (A) There exists a parameter b with units of speed which is the same in all frames. This violates Galilean invariance. This b seems to be an upper bound on speed (as we show later) which seems to contradict Newtonian mechanics.
- (B) A particle with m_0 at rest will be seen to move with v as seen in a frame moving with $-v$. This feature is not simply a statement regarding motion, it implies the existence of momentum which means that a force was applied to the particle at rest. Thus, for a particle with rest mass, the notion of motion linked with x, t is intertwined with E and p .
- (C) The rest mass viewpoint shows a distinct jump in x because $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$ in the rest frame maps to $(x'=0, t'=0)$ and (x', t') such that $x'/t' = v$ in the moving frame. This viewpoint will be shown to lead directly to $E_x - pc = 0$, even without knowing the Lorentz transformation. We suggest that this is linked to a loss of spatial information associated with a change in momentum.

Photon Viewpoint

We have argued in previous notes that one may consider the Lorentz transformation in terms of photons alone. We begin with the notion of a photon as described by Maxwell's equations. In other words, one has two wave-equations:

$$-\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial Electric or Magnetic field} + \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial EI+B} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Here $c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$, where ϵ_0 and μ_0 are the electric and magnetic permittivities.

Three key features arise from Maxwell's result:

- (A) The speed of light c is the same in all frames as ϵ_0 and μ_0 presumably are the same as seen when viewed from moving frames. This violates Galilean invariance, but not Newtonian mechanics because a photon is a wave in this picture.
- (B) The photon is associated with wavelike motion, but the Electric (E) and Magnetic (B) fields seem to represent the medium. This leads to $E = E_0 \cos(\omega t - kx)$ (in the x direction), $B = B_0 \cos(\omega t - k)$ (in the y direction for example) with motion in the z . Furthermore, $E_0 = B_0 c$.

(C) Maxwell's equations lead to the notion of energy density = $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and momentum density = $\frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$, leading to the notion of energy being $\hbar \omega$ and momentum being \hbar/λ , from Planck's work.

Thus, for a photon, the two frame picture involves:

(A) $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$. This allows one to derive a Lorentz transformation containing the speed of light c . (This seems like the b of the rest mass case.)

It seems, however, that one must incorporate the wave feature:

$$-\omega t + kx = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((4))$$

in order for E and p to appear naturally. In fact, if a wave is at the top of a crest as seen in one frame, it should be at the top of a crest in any frame, suggesting that:

$$-Et + px = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((5))$$

Thus, ((5)) is a Lorentz invariant.

Furthermore: velocity = frequency * wavelength $\rightarrow E=pc$

At this point, one has two independent approaches to dealing with moving frames. One is linked with a rest mass, which requires an associated speed parameter b , which is the same in all frames, and intertwines E and p . The second applies only to a photon and only brings in E, p if one considers wave-like motion which leads to $-Et + px$ being an invariant (with respect to moving frames).

The Lorentz Transformations for a Particle with Rest Mass and a Photon are the Same

We first consider deriving the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t . In the moving frame:

$$x' = v g(v/b) t \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v/b) t \quad ((6))$$

We note two things about ((6))

- (A) The first equation contains v and so multiplying by m_0 yields Newton's mv on the RHS. Even though this is not full momentum, it is proportional to it and shows that for the rest mass case that p is directly intertwined with an $x-t$ transformation.
- (B) We notice that $(x=0, t=0)$, $(x=0, t)$ maps to $(x'=0, t'=0)$, (x', t') such that $x'/t' = v$. Thus, there is a jump in x' compared to x because a particle moving with v and having an starting point $(0,0)$ must have a corresponding x' which cannot be 0. We suggest that this is an important point because this discrete jump in x' from $x'=0$ due to motion instead of $x=0$,

$t=0, x=0, t$ suggests that there is a loss of information in space associated with $x'=0$ at $t=0$ becoming x' at t' . This “jump” also occurs for a photon, but one cannot create momentum p by simply multiplying by m_0 (and $g(v)$) in that case. Nevertheless, the jump is there suggesting a kind of discreteness in space, we argue.

Finally, using $x'x' - bb t't' = xx - bbt t$ for $x=0, t$ yields $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ ((7))

Given that there is no photon in this scenario, one may only say that b is an upper bound speed which is the same in all frames. It is thus not associated with any kind of rest mass. If one knows about the photon solution of Maxwell's equations, then c , the speed of light in a vacuum, is a candidate, but it is unusual that it should appear given that the above arguments are strictly for a particle with rest mass (and there are no Maxwell's equations present).

The Lorentz transformation is then:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & v/b g(v) \\ v/b g(v) & g(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((8))$$

One may now try to derive ((8)) strictly for a photon, i.e. $x/t=c$ and $x'/t' = c$. ((9))

The key idea, as argued in previous notes, is that even if there is no rest mass for a photon, the co-ordinate origin acts like a point in a rest frame. It is seen to move in a frame moving with $-v$. We suggest that the same form ((8)) must apply. We use $b=c$ because we have a photon.

$X'x' - cc t't' = xx - cct t = 0$ if one uses ((9))

The LHS is: $gg t t (vv-cc) = 0$ We suggest that:

$$-gg(vv-cc) = cc \text{ or } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((10))$$

No consideration of a particle with rest mass is needed, but the transformation ((8)) which is used for a particle with rest mass is still used because the origin of the co-ordinate axis acts like a rest point.

Thus, it seems that the same Lorentz transformation applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass. We note that ((8)) suggests a jump from $(x=0, t=0)$ to (x',t') in both cases, although in the rest mass case, it is the m_0 which also jumps (moves) and so is linked with momentum, while in the photon case, it is only the origin.

In Parts 1,2 we argued that one may use:

$x'/t'=v$ to find an intertwined E,p,x,t equation that holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass. We note that $x'/t'=v$ is the condition for a particle with rest mass, but it also applies to the origin of the co-ordinate axis of a photon. It is just that the photon is always moving at speed c . The momentum in this case, however, is only that for a particle with rest mass.

$$x'/t'=v \rightarrow m_0cc g(v) x' - cct't'=0 \rightarrow E' x' - ccp't'=0 \quad ((11))$$

In principle, ((11)) should only apply to a particle with rest mass due to its derivation. One sees, however, that ((11)) also holds for a photon if one uses: $E'=p'c$. In other words, the presence of c in momentum and energy expressions for a particle with rest mass allows one to incorporate v into p , leaving an equation with no visible v , which then applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass. We have suggested in Parts 1 and 2, that ((11)) implies that E' and p' are linked with:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((12))$$

A second intertwined x,t,E,p equation comes from the photon result of Maxwell's equations, i.e.

$$E=pc \quad \text{or} \quad -Et+px = 0 \quad \text{using} \quad x/t=c \quad ((13))$$

This should hold only for a photon, but the idea is that $-Et+px$ is an invariant in Maxwell's $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$ for a photon and so:

$$-Et+px = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((14))$$

holds for both a photon and a particle with a rest mass.

Thus, our main idea that special relativity equations hold for both a particle with rest mass and without (photon) at the same time (when written in E,p) form and intertwine E,p,x,t seems to hold.

We argue that the intertwining of x,t and E,p is key because it allows E and p to become linked with spacetime as in ((12)). Already for the particle with rest mass, the jump in x' at t' from $x=0$, due to v is directly associated with the presence of momentum. We suggest that momentum change seems to be linked with a loss of information or discreteness in space, something that is not Newtonian.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the equations of special relativity may be thought of separately in terms of a particle with rest mass, and one without. The rest mass case leads to a Lorentz matrix with a factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$, where b is a maximum speed parameter which is the same in all frames and is not linked with a rest mass. Starting with the notion of a particle with a rest mass, one obtains equations which include the speed of a particle with no rest mass. The two are combined. Secondly, $x'/t'=v$ suggests that x,t are intertwined with E,p and that the jump in x' from $x'=0$ (while $x=0$, $t=0$ and $x=0$, t) is directly linked with momentum. We suggest that this is a hint that p is linked with a wavelength for the particle with a rest mass case.

In the photon case, even though there is no rest mass, there is a rest origin of the co-ordinate axes and the same Lorentz transformation applies, albeit for $b=c$ and $x/t=c$ $x'/t'=c$. In the photon case, there is no mv and so there is no suggestion of p or E being linked with the Lorentz transformation. Nevertheless, one has the same transformation as for the particle with rest mass

which does directly apply to p and E . It is thus reasonable to suggest that E, p for a photon also transform according to this transformation. One may specifically show that they do if one considers Maxwell's equation as described in an above section.

Thus, the key ideas seem to be that special relativistic equations written in terms of E, p apply to both a photon and particle with rest mass and there exist equations linking/intertwining E, p, x, t . The Maxwell equation solution for a photon shows that this intertwining means E and p are linked with period and frequency. The E, p, x, t equations: $E x - p c t = 0$ or $-E t + p x = -E' t' + p' x'$ should be consistent for this (for both a photon and rest mass particle it seems) giving rise to free particle quantum mechanics.